

Supplemental Data for:**Human Gonads Do Not Contribute to the Circulating Pool of 11-Oxygenated Androgens**

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Supplemental data

Supplemental table 1. Study participants

Participant	Sex	Age (years)	Race	BMI (kg/m ²)	Procedure indication
GVS1	F	33	White	25.2	Pelvic congestion syndrome
GVS2	F	31	White	25.2	Varicose veins
GVS3	M	51	White	26.3	Bilateral varicoceles
GVS4	F	40	White	26.5	Varicose veins
GVS5	F	45	White	28.2	Varicose veins
GVS6	F	44	White	28.2	Pelvic congestion syndrome
GVS7	M	31	White	19.3	Bilateral varicoceles
GVS8	M	53	White	40.2	Unilateral varicocele
GVS9	F	31	White	25.7	Pelvic congestion syndrome
GVS10	F	31	White	32.8	Hirsutism
GVS11	M	37	White	37.4	Painful scrotal/pelvic varicosities
BSO1	F	81	White	34.9	Metastatic ovarian carcinoma
BSO2	F	74	White	21.8	Endometrial carcinoma
BSO3	F	43	Asian	31.2	Uterine leiomyomatosis
BSO4	F	54	White	53.0	Mucinous ovarian carcinoma
BSO5	F	57	White	36.6	Myoinvasive endometrial carcinoma
BSO6	F	41	White	22.9	Ovarian ablation for breast cancer
BSO7	F	59	White	25.4	Serous ovarian carcinoma
BSO8	F	67	White	22.8	Metastatic endometrial carcinoma
BSO9	F	51	White	22.1	Endometrial intraepithelial neoplasia
BSO10	F	35	White	39.3	Ovarian ablation for breast cancer
BSO11	F	68	White	24.2	Adenocarcinoma of unknown origin
BSO12	F	59	Black	47.0	Endometrial carcinoma
BSO13	F	51	White	25.2	Serous ovarian carcinoma
BSO14	F	57	White	23.3	Ovarian cyst
BSO15	F	59	White	37.7	Endometrial carcinoma
BSO16	F	63	White	30.0	Ovarian cyst
BSO17	F	45	White	30.0	Endometriosis

Supplemental table 2. Gonadal and peripheral steroid concentrations in 7 women and 4 men.

Steroids	Gonadal (ng/dL)	Peripheral (ng/dL)	Gonadal/peripheral	<i>p</i> value
Cortisol	2293.3 [2096.7- 4023.2]	3213.0 [2162.7-5205.0]	0.9 [0.6-1.0]	0.17
Cortisone	732.0 [683.2-1478.7]	854.8 [677.9-1521.6]	1.1 [0.8-1.2]	0.93
Estradiol	59.0 [46.0-169.2]	8.1 [1.0-14.9]	18.4 [7.0-89.1]	0.002
Estrone	11.5 [8.7-29.4]	5.8 [4.7-7.9]	2.2 [1.6-7.5]	0.008
Progesterone	58.4 [35.9-622.9]	8.4 [5.5-53.6]	14.0 [3.2-33.3]	0.01
17OHP	2481.4 [288.8-4403.1]	33.8 [22.1-124.6]	19.7 [8.5-54.5]	0.01
16OHP	246.8 [35.8-686.9]	7.6 [4.5-19.2]	12.6 [8.1-30.2]	0.002
A4	952.3 [361.6-1513.6]	56.7 [50.6-78.8]	12.1 [7.2-19.8]	0.002
T	67.3 [43.8-7720.6]	34.2 [28.8-415.0]	3.3 [1.4-30.2]	0.03
11OHA4	35.1 [21.6-67.9]	48.7 [36.2-63.8]	0.7 [0.6-1.0]	0.12
11OHT	4.7 [2.4-11.0]	6.2 [3.4-7.5]	0.9 [0.6-1.4]	0.76
11KA4	12.1 [9.5-17.6]	11.1 [7.9-16.3]	1.2 [0.5-1.5]	0.83
11KT	20.1 [13.7-34.3]	18.9 [13.9-25.8]	1.3 [1.0-1.4]	0.12

Gonadal/peripheral represent the median gonadal/peripheral ratio [interquartile range; IQR] and were calculated using the paired gonadal/peripheral ratio for each individual.

Abbreviation: 17OHP, 17 α -hydroxyprogesterone; 16OHP, 16 α -hydroxyprogesterone; A4, androstenedione; T, testosterone; 11OHA4, 11-hydroxyandrostenedione; 11OHT, 11-hydroxytestosterone; 11KA4, 11-ketoandrostenedione; 11KT, 11-ketotestosterone
Values are expressed as median [interquartile range].

Supplemental table 3. Steroid concentrations in peripheral blood samples before and after bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy (BSO) in 17 women.

Steroids	Pre-BSO (ng/dL)	Post-BSO (ng/dL)	Fold change	p value
Cortisol	10066.2 [8088.1-12080.7]	10954.3 [8728.9-13326.1]	1.0 [0.8-1.2]	0.71
Cortisone	2210.4 [1565.8-2397.2]	2009.0 [1554.9-2366.9]	1.1 [0.8-1.3]	0.71
Progesterone	4.6 [3.6-8.2]	4.1 [3.1-5.9]	1.4 [1.0-1.6]	0.02
17OHP	27.1 [12.2-62.1]	15.6 [8.4-25.3]	1.3 [0.9-2.4]	0.03
16OHP	5.9 [4.3-10.6]	5.3 [3.4-6.3]	1.8 [0.9-2.3]	0.03
A4	59.7 [47.7-67.6]	32.7 [27.4-47.8]	1.7 [1.2-2.4]	<0.001
T	24.1 [16.4-32.3]	15.5 [13.7-19.0]	1.6 [1.3-1.8]	<0.001
11OHA4	183.6 [130.7-247.0]	148.2 [105.3-224.5]	1.3 [0.9-1.7]	0.21
11OHT	18.3 [11.8-24.3]	12.9 [5.6-22.2]	1.1 [1.0-1.7]	0.09
11KA4	19.1 [15.9-42.2]	22.3 [16.3-28.2]	1.1 [0.7-1.4]	0.31
11KT	30.8 [27.5-46.2]	22.4 [11.1-37.9]	1.3 [0.8-2.4]	0.24

Fold change represent the median pre-BSO/post-BSO ratio [interquartile range; IQR] and were calculated using the paired pre-BSO/post-BSO ratio in each individual.

Abbreviation: 17OHP, 17 α -hydroxyprogesterone; 16OHP, 16 α -hydroxyprogesterone; A4, androstenedione; T, testosterone; 11OHA4, 11-hydroxyandrostenedione; 11OHT, 11-hydroxytestosterone; 11KA4, 11-ketoandrostenedione; 11KT, 11-ketotestosterone
Values are expressed as median [interquartile range].